

THE ROLE OF INVESTMENT IN CONSTRUCTION AND PUBLIC INVESTMENT POLICY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6527345>

Safarov Sindor Sanjar o'g'li

A student of Tashkent State University of Economics

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Tel: +998 93 240 33 08

Annotation: *This article discusses the specific role of investment activities in the construction industry and the investment policy of the state. The importance of investment in the modernization of the economy, the level of development of each country as well as the development of the economy and economic growth in many respects depends on the investment process in the country, the relevant economic analysis and conclusions are developed.*

Keywords: *investment attraction, investment process, investment activity, public investment policy: regions, industry and enterprise investment policy, construction.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье рассматривается специфическая роль инвестиционной деятельности в строительной отрасли и инвестиционная политика государства. Значение инвестиций в модернизацию экономики, уровень развития каждой страны, а также развитие экономики и экономический рост во многом зависят от инвестиционного процесса в стране, разрабатываются соответствующие экономические анализы и выводы.*

Ключевые слова: *привлечение инвестиций, инвестиционный процесс, инвестиционная деятельность, государственная инвестиционная политика: регионы, промышленность и инвестиционная политика предприятий, строительство.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada investitsiyon faoliyatning qurilish sohasida tutgan o'ziga xos o'rni hamda davlatning investitsiyon siyosati haqida fikr yuritiladi. Shuningdek, iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiyalash sharoitida investitsiya faoliyati muhim ahamiyat kasb etishi, har bir mamlakatning rivojlanish darajasi, ya'ni iqtisodiyotning rivojlanishi va iqtisodiy o'sishi ko'p jihatdan mamlakatdagi investitsion jarayonlarga bog'liqligi haqida mavzu yoritilib, tegishli iqtisodiy tahlillar va xulosalar ishlab chiqilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *investitsiyalarni jalb qilish, investitsiyon jarayon, investitsion faoliyat, davlat investitsiya siyosati: hududlar, tarmoq va korxonalar investitsiya siyosati, qurilish ishlari.*

Introduction At any time in the world, attracting new technologies to the economy, attracting investment in industries, is one of the main directions of modernization of the economy.

At present, changes and structural reforms are being carried out in all sectors of the Uzbek economy. The implementation of such reforms directly depends on the investment process in the country, the investment policy of the state, its priorities and the investment activity of enterprises in the country. During the short period of our independence, a number of practical measures have been taken to increase and strengthen investment activity, a number of laws and regulations governing investment activities have been issued and are being implemented.

The importance of investment policy in this direction is enormous. Because investments stimulate structural changes in the economy, technical and technological innovations, the implementation of reconstruction of enterprises, increase the country's export and import potential. In this regard, the state of Uzbekistan is pursuing its investment policy.

That is why it is necessary to attract large amounts of capital in the tourism, socio-economic and construction sectors of the country.

The main part Our country has also created an investment climate that meets international standards. The government has created all the facilities for investors. Therefore, the first direction of the Comprehensive Development Program of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, 'Strategy of The Actions' was aimed at this area, whereas the aims to create ample opportunities for state and society building were intended to focus.

Investment policy is a set of mechanisms and methods aimed at developing and supporting priority sectors of the economy, the transition from a centralized investment process to a decentralized investment process, support for priority investment projects. In the implementation of public investment policy, more priority is given to the creation of small businesses, enterprises with foreign investment and the elimination of existing shortcomings, rapid resolution of problems and the creation of a favorable economic, investment environment for investment.

Public investment policy consists of regional, sectoral and enterprise investment policies, which are interrelated. Territorial investment policy is a set of measures to be implemented in an area that allows for the effective use of investment, taking into account the interests of the population, the region and the

investor. Sectoral investment policy is the sectors that ensure the development of the country's economy, the export of industrial products, the introduction of import-substituting production, investment support for scientific and technological progress.

Investment in the economy of Uzbekistan, first of all, through the mobilization of domestic resources, has become a key priority in the accelerated modernization, technical and technological re-equipment and further development of key sectors of our economy and the construction of social infrastructure.

In January-April of 2019, a total of 21240.8 billion soums of construction work was performed in the Republic of Uzbekistan while the growth rate was 107.9% compared to the same period last year.

In the current period, the total volume of construction work performed by large construction companies amounted to 5723.8 billion soums.

Compared to the same period last year, 4.8% more work was done, the share of total construction work decreased by 0.9% compared to the same period last year.

The total volume of construction works - 21240.8 billion soums compared to the same period last year - 107.9% Non-governmental organizations - 20208.7 billion soums. State-owned organizations - 1032.1 billion soums.

The volume of construction work performed by construction companies in January-April 2020 amounted to 6,578.0 billion soums.

One of the important tasks of investment policy is to regulate the investment process in the context of modernization of the economy, to create the economic basis for determining the correct direction and distribution, to provide conditions for the implementation of the economic growth can be achieved in exactly the same way.

The volume of construction work performed by small enterprises and micro-firms in the current period increased sharply compared to other organizations engaged in construction work. They accounted for 55.2% of the total construction work, a decrease of 0.2% compared to the same period last year.

In addition, the volume of construction work, which contributed to them, amounted to 11727.6 billion soums, which is 108.1% compared to the same period last year.

The share of construction work in the informal sector increased by 1.0 percentage points compared to the previous year and amounted to 17.8% and amounted to 3789.4 billion soums. Compared to the same period of last year, it was 112.5%.

The main part of construction work by type of economic activity consisted of the development of construction projects, construction of residential and non-residential buildings and construction of non-residential buildings.

The share of construction works performed by large construction companies in the construction of buildings and structures amounted to 27.3%, a decrease of 1.9 percentage points from the previous year.

The share of small businesses and micro-firms in this type of activity decreased by 0.2% compared to the previous year and amounted to 49.2%.

The share of the informal sector increased by 2.1 percentage points compared to the previous year and amounted to 23.5%.

Conclusion Bugungi kunda 37 mingdan ortiq qurilish tashkilotlari mavjud bo'lib, koronavirus pandemiyasi paytida o'tkazilgan monitoring kuzatuvlariga ko'ra qurilish ishlari vaqtincha to'xtaganligi aniqlandi, natijada mavjud vaziyat mamlakatdagi qurilish ishlari hajmiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatdi.

Today, there are more than 37,000 construction companies, and monitoring during the coronavirus pandemic has revealed a temporary halt in construction, as a result of which the current situation has had a negative impact on the volume of construction work in the country.

As a result, the work performed by small businesses and micro-firms, which accounted for 54.3% of the total construction work, decreased by 15.6% compared to the same period last year.

REFERENCES:

1. Fundamentals of Investment and Leasing– K.Z. Homitov, A.N.Mahmudov
2. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis for 2020
3. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Investment Program of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017"
4. O'zbekiston respublikasida qurilish sohasidagi investitsion muhit - H.X.Iskandarov H.Q.Mo'minova. Article
5. Safarov S.S. The role of investment in economic growth. Collection of abstracts of the international scientific-practical conference "The role of management and corporate governance in the development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan." May 20, 2020. –T.: –2020. pages 458-460.
6. Stat.uz - website

7. Lex.uz - website

